

Supplementary Material

Baseline risk

Baseline risks were based on German population data (Federal Health Reporting 2014; German Centre for Cancer Registry Data (ZfKD) 2013). The data is provided stratified in 5 year age categories. In order not to underestimate total cancer risk when summing over all organs, incidence and mortality rates of unknown cancer types (ICD codes C76, C80) were redistributed. The observed number of cases of a certain endpoint for a given age category were considered to follow from a Poisson distribution with rate λ . This rate λ may deviate from the observed population rate in particular for very rare diseases or at young ages. Therefore, λ was sampled from the age-specific number of incidence cases. In order to avoid discontinuities, rates were interpolated linearly between age categories.

For lung cancer (ICD-10 C33, C34) the baseline rates were personalized according to smoking behavior. This required separating the population lung cancer risk into the contributions from subgroups of different smoking behavior. For this purpose, smoking intensity dependent relative risk RR_s was adopted from (Pesch et al. 2012), differentiating between the following subgroups: non-smokers, former smokers, <10 cigarettes per day, 10-20 cigarettes per day, 20-30 cigarettes per day, and more than 30 cigarettes per day. Uncertainty in relative risks was sampled from a log-normal distribution based on the published confidence intervals. Age and sex dependent smoking prevalence p_s was taken from (Piontek D et al. 2016). However, their classification of different smoking intensities misses the highest smoking category present in (Pesch et al. 2012). Therefore, it was assumed that 17% of female smokers with more than 20 cigarettes per day actually smoke more than 30 cigarettes a day (Pesch et al. 2012). Moreover, prevalence of smoking is presented in (Piontek D et al. 2016) only up to an age of 65. For ages above 65, data from (Zeiber J et al. 2017) was thus used for prevalence of non-smokers, former smokers and smokers, and the shares of subgroups of different smoking intensities were kept from the highest age group in (Piontek D et al. 2016). Statistical uncertainty was taken into account by sampling the prevalence from the Dirichlet distribution, assuming conservatively 500 cases per age category in the data. Finally, lung cancer rates in non-smokers $\lambda_{non-smoker}$ can be deduced from writing the population lung cancer rate λ as the sum of contributions from the different subgroups in smoking intensity s , each with rate $RR_s \lambda_{non-smoker}$:

$$\lambda = \sum_s p_s RR_s \lambda_{non-smoker}$$

References

- Federal Health Reporting (2014) Deaths, Mortality figures (from 1998). Joint Service by RKI and Destatis. <http://www.gbe-bund.de/>.
- German Centre for Cancer Registry Data (ZfKD) (2013) Database Query with estimates for cancer incidence, prevalence and survival in Germany, based on data of the population based cancer registries. Robert Koch Institute, <https://www.krebsdaten.de/database>.

Pesch B et al. (2012) Cigarette smoking and lung cancer--relative risk estimates for the major histological types from a pooled analysis of case-control studies *Int J Cancer* 131:1210-1219 doi:10.1002/ijc.27339

Piontek D, Atzendorf J, Gomes de Matos E, Kraus L (2016) Kurzbericht Epidemiologischer Suchtsurvey 2015. IFT Institut für Therapieforschung, Munich

Zeiger J, Kuntz B, Lange C (2017) Rauchen bei Erwachsenen in Deutschland *Journal of Health Monitoring* 2:59-65 doi:10.17886/RKI-GBE-2017-030